

Reactions of Metal β -Diketonates-I. Reactions of Bis (Acetylacetonato) Nickel(II) with Chelating Ligands

K. DEY and S. K. SEN

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal.

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Reactions of bis (acetylacetonato) nickel(II), $Ni(acac)_2$, with various chelating ligands in different conditions have been described. When the reactions are performed in non-aqueous media (e. g. toluene, dichloromethane, etc.), six-coordinate heterochelates of the type $Ni(acac)_2(L-L)$ (where, $L-L$ = bidentate ligands) have been isolated. The same reactions with chelating ligands containing at least one $-NH_2$ group, when performed in ethanol or other solvents containing little water, yielded corresponding Schiff base (condensation products of acetylacetonato and chelating amino ligands) complexes of nickel(II).

The newly synthesized complexes have been characterized with the help of elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibilities, infrared, ultraviolet, and visible spectral data.

NOT much work has been done on the reactions of bis(acetylacetonato) metal(II), $M(acac)_2$, with chelating ligands containing a primary amine group, although the reactions of $M^{II}(acac)_2$ with monodentate ligands are well known¹. We have undertaken a scheme to study the reactions of $M^{II}(acac)_2$ with various chelating ligands (containing at least one primary amine group) in different solvents and at different temperatures. This paper describes our initial observation on the reactions of bis(acetylacetonato) nickel(II), $Ni(acac)_2$, with ethylenediamine (=en), 1, 3-diaminopropane (=tn), 1, 3-diaminopropane-2-ol (=tna-H), ethanolamine (=ena-H), glycine (=gly-H), orthoaminophenol (=oap-H), anthranilic acid (aa-H), semicarbazide (sc H), and thiosemicarbazide (=tsc-H). This paper also includes the reactions of $Ni(acac)_2$ with N-phenylsalicylaldehyde (=SALAN-H), N-(2-hydroxy) phenyl salicylaldehyde (=SALOAP-H₂) and N,N'-ethylene-bis(salicylaldehyde)(=SALEN-H₂). During the course of this work a series of new mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) have been isolated and characterized. While our work was in progress, a note on the reactions of $Ni(acac)_2$ with ethylenediamine and N,N'-disubstituted ethylenediamine had appeared² in which cis-octahedral $Ni(acac)(L-L)$ complexes (where, $L-L$ = ethylenediamine, or substituted ethylenediamine) were isolated.

The following abbreviations for the Schiff bases of acetylacetonato have been used in the present study: ACACENA-H₂ = N-2-hydroxyethylacetylacetonimine; ACACGLY-H₂ = N-2-carboxymethylacetylacetonimine; ACACSC-H₂ = acetylacetonato semicarbazone; and ACACTSC-H₂ = acetylacetonato thiosemicarbazone.

* For correspondence.

Experimental

Solvents and chemicals were purified and dried by usual procedures. Nickel was estimated as dimethylglyoximate after decomposing the complex with a mixture of $H_2SO_4-HNO_3$ and nitrogen was estimated either by Kjeldahl semimicro method or by Dumas method. The elemental analyses of C and H were done either by Alfred Bernhardt Micro-analytical Laboratory, West Germany or C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr pellets by C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured in a Gouy balance. Electronic spectra were recorded in a Beckman-DU-2 or Spectromom Spectrophotometer. Conductances were measured by Mullard conductivity bridge.

Preparation of the complexes :

Bis(acetylacetonato) nickel(II) dihydrate, $Ni(acac)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ was prepared by a published method³. It was dehydrated by azeotropic distillation from toluene solution.

$Ni(acac)_2(en)$, (I) : A mixture of $Ni(acac)_2$ (0.005 mole) and EN(0.005 mole) in 60 ml of dry toluene was refluxed for about 2 hours. The blue solution was filtered while hot, which on concentration and cooling yielded blue crystalline compound. These were filtered, washed with ethanol-toluene mixture (50:50, v/v) and dried in vacuo, yield \approx 50%. Compounds $Ni(acac)_2(tn)$, (II); $Ni(acac)_2(tna-H)$, (III); and $Ni(acac)_2(ena-H)$, (IV) can be prepared similarly.

$Ni(ACACENA)_2 \cdot H_2O(V)$: This light blue crystalline compound was precipitated out when the mixture

of Ni(acac)₂·2H₂O or Ni(acac)₂ (0.005 mole) in 30 ml of ethanol and ena-H (0.005 mole) in 15 ml of ethanol was refluxed on water-bath for 2 hours. The complex was separated while the solution was hot and washed with cold ethanol and dried in vacuo. Yield~60%, m.p.~225° (dec.)

Analogous reactions of Ni(acac)₂·2H₂O with oap-H and gly-H in boiling toluene gave Ni(acac)(oap)·2H₂O, (VI) and H[Ni(acac)(ACACGLY)H₂O], (VII) respectively.

Ni(ACACGLY)H₂O, (VIII): The green complex (VII) was heated in the range 230-260° to yield a brown mass. This mass was extracted with ethanol-acetone mixture, and the brown extract yielded brown solid complex on adding few drops of water.

Ni(ACACSC-H)₂, (IX): The reaction of Ni(acac)₂·2H₂O or Ni(acac)₂ (0.005 mole) with sc-H (0.005 mole) in aqueous acetone under reflux gave this crystalline complex.

Ni(ACACTSC-H)₂, (X): Analogously this complex was obtained from the refluxed solution and the brown filtrate, on reduction of its volume and cooling, gave Ni(acac)(tsc), (XI). It was washed with acetone and dried in vacuo.

Ni(acac)(SALAN)H₂O, (XII): The equimolar (0.005 mole) mixture of Ni(acac)₂·H₂O and SALAN-H₂ in 50 ml of ethanol was refluxed on water-bath for one hour. The green solution, thus obtained, was filtered and the volume was reduced. This gave light green crystals on standing, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl₂. Yield~50%.

The compounds Ni(SALOAP)H₂O, (XIII) and Ni(SALEN), (XIV) were obtained analogously.

Results and Discussion

Syntheses of the nickel(II) chelates

The title complex Ni(acac)₂ reacts with en,tn,tna-H, or ena-H in boiling toluene (or dichloromethane, or

dichlorobenzene) and the blue or greenish blue crystalline solid complexes obtained from the reaction mixture have the general composition Ni(acac)₂(L-L) (see experimental), where 'L-L' stands for en, (I); tn, (II); tna-H, (III); or ena-H, (IV). On the other hand, analogous reactions of Ni(acac)₂·2H₂O or Ni(acac)₂ with oap-H and gly-H in boiling toluene yielded Ni(acac)(oap)·2H₂O, (VI) and H[Ni(acac)(ACACGLY)H₂O], (VII) respectively. It is interesting to note that Ni(acac)₂·2H₂O reacts with ena-H in boiling ethanol and light blue crystalline complex, bis[N-(2-hydroxyethyl) acetylacetonimine] nickel(II) monohydrate, Ni(ACACENA-H)₂·H₂O, (V) is obtained. However, the reaction of the title compound with semicarbazide hydrochloride in boiling aqueous acetone yields light green crystalline complex Ni(ACACSC-H)₂, (IX). Analogous reaction between Ni(acac)₂·2H₂O and thiosemicarbazide in aqueous ethanol yields two compounds: a green complex Ni(ACACTSC-H)₂, (X), and a brown complex Ni(acac)(tsc), (XI). Another interesting mixed ligand complex Ni(acac)(SALAN)H₂O, (XII) has been obtained by the partial replacement of acetylacetonate anion by N-phenylsalicylaldimine anion when the reaction is carried out in boiling ethanol. However, total replacement of acetylacetonate anions are observed when Ni(acac)₂·2H₂O reacts with SALOAP-H₂ (in ethanol), BSEN-H₂ (in ethanol), aa-H (in ethanol), or gly-H (in water-acetone-ethanol mixture) to yield Ni(SALOAP)H₂O, (XIII); or Ni(SALEN), (XIV); Ni(aa)₂·2H₂O (XV), or Ni(gly)₂·2H₂O (XVI).

Properties of the nickel(II) chelates:

The elemental analyses (Table-1) support the formulations of the isolated chelates, and the complexes are indefinitely stable in air. The complex (I) is insoluble in water, benzene and ethanol, but partially soluble in pyridine and DMSO. The complexes (IV) and (V) are insoluble in water, benzene, and chloroform, but soluble in methanol, ethanol, pyridine, DMSO and DMF. The complex (IX) is insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in ethanol, carbon tetrachloride and DMSO. The compounds (X) to (XII) are either moderately or completely soluble in common organic solvents.

All these complexes, except Ni(ACACGLY)H₂O, (VIII); Ni(acac)(tsc), (XI); Ni(acac)(SALAN)H₂O,

TABLE-1: ELEMENTARY ANALYSES AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	M.P. °C	Found %				Calculated %				μ _{eff} (B.M.) (Room Temp.)
		C	H	N	Ni	C	H	N	Ni	
[Ni(acac) ₂ (en)], (I)	300	46.00	7.02	8.75	18.50	45.42	6.94	8.83	18.61	3.24
[Ni(acac) ₂ (tn)], (II)	270 (dec.)	47.58	7.00	8.53	17.95	47.13	7.25	8.46	17.82	3.15
[Ni(acac) ₂ (tna-H)], (III)	250 (dec.)	45.00	6.52	8.22	17.25	44.95	6.92	8.07	17.00	3.28
[Ni(acac) ₂ (ena-H)], (IV)	230-233	45.46	6.78	4.58	18.92	45.29	6.60	4.40	18.56	3.03
Ni(ACACENA-H) ₂ ·H ₂ O, (V)	250 (dec.)	45.50	7.20	7.96	15.98	46.54	7.20	7.75	16.35	3.21
[Ni(acac)(oap)]·2H ₂ O, (VI)	280 (dec.)	44.00	5.40	4.88	20.01	43.71	5.63	4.63	19.54	3.48
H[Ni(acac)(ACACGLY)H ₂ O], (VII)	260 (dec.)	43.72	5.55	4.33	17.93	43.51	5.74	4.23	17.82	3.62
Ni(ACACGLY)(H ₂ O), (VIII)	—	36.80	4.65	6.11	25.64	36.21	4.74	6.03	25.41	3.26
Ni(ACACTSC-H) ₂ , (X)	200	39.02	5.42	22.50	15.88	38.82	5.39	22.64	15.91	3.08
Ni(ACACTSC-H) ₂ , (XI)	—	36.00	5.21	20.75	14.70	35.74	4.96	20.84	14.64	3.26
Ni(acac)(SALAN), (XII)	—	29.25	4.40	16.88	23.80	29.02	4.43	16.93	23.79	3.26
[Ni(acac)(SALAN)]H ₂ O, (XIII)	—	57.88	5.23	3.98	16.26	58.08	5.11	3.76	15.86	do
[Ni(SALOAP)H ₂ O], (XIV)	300	54.70	3.80	5.15	20.56	54.17	3.81	4.86	20.48	do
[Ni(SALEN)], (XIV)	—	—	—	8.87	18.02	—	—	8.64	17.90	do

(XII); Ni(SALOAP)H₂O (XIII); and Ni(SALEN), (XIV), are spin triplets with magnetic moments lying in the range 3.03 to 3.62 B.M. (Table-1). The complex (VIII), and (XI) to (XIV) are found to be diamagnetic (Table-1). The magnetic moments of the compounds (VI) and (VII) are found to be 3.48 B.M. and 3.62 B.M. respectively.

The magnetic moments (3.03-3.28 B.M.) of the compounds, excluding (VIII) and (XI) to (XIV), are within the normal octahedral range of nickel(II)⁴. The slightly high magnetic moments of (VI) and (VII) may arise due to further distortion in geometry. Square planar geometry may be proposed for the diamagnetic complexes (VIII) and (XI) to (XIV).

The electronic spectra of the present nickel(II) complexes in nujol mull, ethanol and methanol have been recorded (Table-2). Three bands have been obtained in the regions (a) 9,700-10,800 cm⁻¹; (b) 13,400-14,500 cm⁻¹; and (c) 15,800-17,200 cm⁻¹. In the case of Ni(ACACSC-H)₂(IX) and Ni(ACACTSC-H)₂, (X), one additional band has been observed in each case in the region (d) 17,000-18,500 cm⁻¹. The electronic spectra

It is difficult (on the basis of the present data) to ascertain whether the bands observed in the region (b) is due to spin-forbidden transition or a low-symmetry component of the ν_1 band.

Considering the crystalline field of O_h symmetry around nickel(II) ion in these complexes the Racah parameters, B, have been calculated for some of these complexes using the matrices given by Tanabe and Sugano^{5,6}. It is clear that the values of B (Table-2) are, in many cases, fairly greater than the free ion value (B₀ = 1084 cm⁻¹). This shows the distortion from O_h symmetry. The energy values for the spin-forbidden transition ³A_{2g}(F) → ¹E_g(D) have been calculated assuming C = 4 B (Table-3), and in many cases have been found to differ from the experimental values observed for the present nickel(II) complexes. This again supports distortion from O_h symmetry^{7,8}. Thus, we tentatively suggest that the bands observed in the region (b) is not due to ³A_{2g}(F) → ¹E_g(D) transition, instead it may be a low-symmetry component of the ν_1 band. In absence of required splitted bands, the distortion parameters remain unexplored and thus further scrutiny of the observed bands are not possible.

TABLE-2 : ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND RACA H PARAMETERS OF SOME NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES (B₀ = 1084 cm⁻¹)

Complex	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g} (F)	³ A _{2g} (F) → ¹ E _g (D)	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (F)	B	
				(from ν_2)	from ¹ E _g (D)
Ni(acac) ₂ (en), (I)	10,780 (obs) (10D _q)	13,500 (obs)sh 12,245 (cal)	17,000 (obs) (ν_2)	786	868
Ni(acac) ₂ (tn), (II)	10,000 (obs) (10D _q)	13,520 (obs) not calculated	16,900 (obs) (ν_2)	1296 > B ₀	871
Ni(acac) ₂ (tna-H), (III)	10,000 (obs) (10D _q)	13,500 (obs) sh not calculated	16,985 (obs) (ν_2)	1383 > B ₀	629
Ni(acac) ₂ (ena-H), (IV)	9,850 (obs) (10D _q)	13,480 (obs) sh 13,590 (cal)	16,000 (obs) (ν_2)	877	869
Ni(ACACENA-H) ₂ , H ₂ O, (V)	10,500 (obs) (10D _q)	13,500 (obs) sh 13,600 (cal)	17,200 (obs) (ν_2)	999	659
Ni(acac)(oap)] 2H ₂ O, (VI)	9,700 (obs) (10D _q)	13,500 (obs) 15,090 (cal)	16,000 (obs) (ν_2)	978	611
H[Ni(acac)(ACACGLY)], H ₂ O, (VII)	9,800 (obs) (10D _q)	13,400 (obs) sh not calculated	16,500 (obs) (ν_2)	1385 > B ₀	617
Ni(ACACSC-H) ₂ , (IX)	9,800 (obs) (10D _q)	14,000 (obs) sh 14,415 (cal)	16,000 (obs) 18,500 (obs) (ν_2)	907	618
Ni(ACACTSC-H) ₂ , (X)	10,000 (obs) (10D _q)	14,500 (obs) sh 11,510 (cal)	15,800 (obs) 17,240 (obs) sh (ν_2)	738	632

of some of these complexes, when measured upto 45,000 cm⁻¹ range, show two or three bands in the range 20,000-45,000 cm⁻¹ and their extinctions are very high. No attempts have been made to assign these high energy bands to spin-allowed transition ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν_2 in O_h) because of the presence of charge-transfer bands due to ligands in this region. However, the spectra are clearly in accord with a pseudooctahedral geometry and band assignments may be made as follows :

- region (a) : ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν_1)
- region (b) : ³A_{2g}(F) → ¹E_g(D) (or, split components of ν_1)
- region (c) : ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν_2)

Fig.1.

It is quite clear from i.r. spectral analyses that acetylacetonate coordinates as oxygen-bonded chelating anion while ethylenediamine and ethanolamine function

as neutral bidentate ligands, in the complexes (I) and (IV). The mixed ligand complex $H[Ni(acac)(ACACGLY)H_2O]$, (VII) showed four bands in the range 1630 to 1545 cm^{-1} . The $C=C$, $C=N$ and $C=O$ ($acac$) stretches are clearly observed at 1630 cm^{-1} , 1620 cm^{-1} and 1545 cm^{-1} respectively. The systematic presence of $C=C$, $C=N$ and $C=O$ stretches is a necessary condition for the mixed ligand formulation involving an acetylacetonate anion and a dibasic Schiff base derived from the condensation of acetylacetone and glycine. However, it is very difficult to assign all the bands observed in the region 1630 - 1545 cm^{-1} , as the group $-C-O-Ni$ is present in the complex, $\nu_{C=O}$ of which

will absorb $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The coordinated water band in the above complex observed at 800 cm^{-1} .⁹ (Tentatively assigned, as proper assignments are difficult in such ligand systems). A strong band appeared at $\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complex is difficult to assign in the present structure. The presence of some glycinate nickel(II) impurity may be one of the important reasons for the appearance of such band. The pseudooctahedral geometry of the complex (VII), as inferred from electronic spectra and μ_{eff} value, is also supported by the present formulation with the help of i.r. spectral data.

Fig. 2

It is interesting to note that heat treatment (230 - 260°) on the green complex(VII) converted it to a brown complex $Ni(ACACGLY)H_2O$, (VIII). The nujol mull electronic spectrum of the complex showed one shoulder at $19,250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on the high energy charge transfer band. This band may be tentatively assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transition ($b_{2g} \rightarrow b_{1g}$), and a square planar geometry may be proposed for this complex.

The reaction of $Ni(acac)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ with thiosemicarbazide in refluxing ethanol yielded two products: one green, paramagnetic, pseudooctahedral, $Ni(ACACTSCH)_2$, (X), and the other brown, diamagnetic, square planar $Ni(acac)(tsc)$, (XI). The appearance of a band in the form of a shoulder at $19,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the electronic spectrum of (XI) supports this square-planar geometry for the complex under discussion. On the other hand, the complex (X) has been inferred to be pseudooctahedral from its μ_{eff} value and electronic absorption spectral data (see previous discussion). The infrared spectral data support the mixed ligand formulation for the complex (XI) involving acetylacetonate

anion and monobasic chelating thiosemicarbazide. On the otherhand, two moles of acetylacetone thiosemicarbazone (monobasic ligand) coordinated with nickel(II) ion to yield the complex (X). The three i.r. bands observed in the range 3500 - 3150 cm^{-1} in the complex (XI), may be safely assigned as due to ν_{N-H} vibrations. However, it is extremely difficult to assign the four bands observed in 1625 - 1525 cm^{-1} range. It may be inferred that these four bands demonstrate the presence of ν_{C-C} and ν_{C-O} (oxygen-bonded chelating acetylacetonate ion), δ_{NH_2} and amide II band, along with ν_{C-N} (chelating thiosemicarbazide anion)^{10,11}. Analogously, three bands in range 3500 - 3240 cm^{-1} observed in the complex (X) may be explained as due to ν_{N-H} . The appearance of four bands at 1638 , 1605 , 1570 and 1522 cm^{-1} may be taken as a proof of the presence of $\nu_{C=C}$, $\nu_{C=O}$ (acetylacetonate ion), $\nu_{C=N}$ (imine linkage) and δ_{NH_2} , and amide II band. The $\nu_{C=S}$ in the free ligand observed at 1458 cm^{-1} and 785 cm^{-1} , while these bands appeared at 1460 cm^{-1} and 782 cm^{-1} respectively showing the uncoordinated nature of $C=S$ bond. The important infrared absorption bands observed in the complexes $Ni(ACACENA-H)_2 \cdot H_2O$, (V), $[Ni(acac)(SALAN)] \cdot H_2O$, (XII), and $Ni(SALOAP)H_2O$, (XIII) are in accord with the formulations of the compounds.

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